

A LITERATURE SURVEY ON ELECTRO CHEMICAL MACHINING AND ITS RECENT DEVELOPMENTS

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Abstract

Electro Chemical Machining (ECM) is an advanced metal-working technique for manufacturing micro-textures by utilizing the electrolysis process on the metallic workpiece surface. It is particularly effective for machining difficult-to-cut materials (e.g., high-strength, tough, hard, and brittle alloys, super-alloys), complex-shaped parts, and regions difficult to access using conventional methods. ECM is capable of performing specialized tasks such as drilling very small, deep, or curved holes. With advancements and integration with newer technologies, ECM finds extensive application in environments involving extreme temperature, loading, friction, wear, and corrosion—especially in energy, transportation, and machinery manufacturing industries. This paper presents a literature review on recent developments in ECM and highlights its advantages over traditional machining processes.

Keywords: *Electro chemical Machining, Electrolyte, Electrolysis, Material Removal Rate, Electrode, WECM, Fuzzy logic.*

1. Introduction

Electro Chemical Machining (ECM) works under the principle of electrolysis by removing the unwanted material and suitable for manufacturing complicated and intricate shapes. Almost all kinds of electro conductive metals and alloys can be electro-chemically machined, especially high-alloyed nickel - or titanium-based ones, as well as hardened materials. As it is a contactless procedure with no heat input, the process is not subject to any of the disadvantages experienced with traditional machining methods, e.g. tool wear, mechanical stresses, micro fissures caused by heat transfer or the need for subsequent deburring operations. All electrochemical machining processes are characterized by stress-free stock removal, gentle transitions and top-quality surfaces without burr formation. During the process the metal work piece is dissolved (Machining) locally through electricity (Electro) and chemistry (Chemical) until it reaches the required complex 3D end shape. ECM finds its application areas as aerospace, automotive, construction, medical equipment, micro-systems and power supply industries. The process is similar to electrical discharge machining (EDM) in that a high current is passed between an electrode and the part, through an electrolytic material removal process having a negatively charged electrode (cathode), a conductive fluid (electrolyte), and a conductive work piece (anode) however, in ECM there is no tool wear. The ECM cutting tool is guided along the desired path close to the work but without touching the piece. Unlike EDM, however, no sparks are created. High metal removal rates are possible with ECM, with no thermal or mechanical stresses being transferred to the part, and mirror surface finishes can be achieved. In the ECM process, a cathode is advanced into an anode. The pressurized electrolyte is injected at a set temperature to the area being cut. The gap between the tool and the work piece varies within 80 800 micrometers.

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As electrons cross the gap, material from the work piece is dissolved, as the tool forms the desired shape in the work piece. The electrolytic fluid carries away the metal hydroxide formed in the process. ECM can cut small or odd-shaped angles, intricate contours or cavities for hard and exotic metals, such as titanium aluminides, high nickel, cobalt, and rhenium alloys. Both external and internal geometries can be machined. The ECM process is most widely used to produce complicated shapes such as turbine blades with good surface finish for difficult to machine materials.

2. Working Principle of Electro Chemical Machining

In ECM, the work piece material is removed by electrolysis. A tool, usually copper (negative electrode), of the desired shape is kept at a fixed distance away from the electrically conductive work piece (positive electrode), which is immersed in a bath containing a fast flowing electrolyte and connected to a power supply. The work piece is then dissolved by an electrochemical reaction to the shape of the tool. The electrolyte also removes the ‘sludge’ produced at the work piece surface. The value consistency of an inter electrode gap (IEG) in ECM varies from 80- 800 micrometers depends on various factors, namely electrolyte temperature, the thickness of the passive layer produced and the efficiency of IEG residue removal. These factors play a vital role in promoting a constant current density at the IEG which results in obtaining a better Material Removal Rate (MRR) and surface roughness (Sathiyamoorthy et al., 2015). The main disadvantage of the ECM is as it requires the need for electrical conductors for the electrode materials and the work piece. The removal rate of material decreases linearly with applied voltage and decreases nonlinearly with the feed rate of the devices.

Figure 1: Components of ECM Principle

The components of ECM principle (Chaudhary D et al., 2014 & Kalpakjian S et al., 2013) are categorized under 4 systems,

3.1 DC power supply – the machining rate in ECM is proportional to electric current density. For achieving the higher rate, the ECM process is performed at a high direct current exceeding 1000A. The gap between the tool and the work piece must be low for high-pitched correctness, thus the voltage must be small to prevent a short circuit. The voltage of the process is 5-25 V.

3.2 Electrolyte circulation system – the products of the electrochemical reaction should be removed from the gap between the work piece and the tool. Accumulation of the reaction products causes decrease of the process efficiency and reduction of the rate of machining. Therefore the electrolyte flow speed should be high. Commonly it is in the range 300-3,000 m/min (1,000-10,000 ft/min). The inlet pressure should be in between 0.15-3 MPa. The electrolyte system should comprise a fairly strong pump. The electrolyte is continuously filtered in order to trap the precipitated reaction products (sludge).

3.3 Control system – Electrical parameters of the process (voltage and current), tool feed speed and parameters of electrolyte circulation system (inlet and outlet pressure of electrolyte, temperature of electrolyte) are controlled by the control system, which provide stable and efficient operation of the unit. The current is carried between the tool and the work piece through electrolyte, the produced heat is dissipated by the liquid electrolytic solution, the product of machining is removed by the solution and it keeps the reactions continuous by supplying the elements necessary for the reaction. For different types of machined materials, different types of electrolytes are used in ECM. (Z Pandilov, 2017)

- **Sodium chloride (NaCl)** at the concentration of 20% - for ferrous alloys (e.g. Steels and cast irons and cobalt alloys)
- **Sodium nitrate (NaNO₃)** - for ferrous alloys
- **Hydrochloric acid (HCl)** - for nickel alloys
- **A mixture of sodium chloride (NaCl) and sulfuric acid (H₂SO₄)** - for nickel alloys
- **A mixture of 10% hydrofluoric acid (HF), 10% hydrochloric acid (HCl), 10% nitric acid (HNO₃)** - for titanium alloys
- **Sodium hydroxide (NaOH)** - for tungsten carbide (WC)

The selection of the electrolyte should be done by considering the following matters: required machining rate, required dimensional accuracy and surface texture and integrity. The electrolyte should possess several important properties.

- High electrical conductivity
- High specific heat
- Low viscosity
- Chemically stable and active to cause the better metal or material removal rate
- Not forming any type of excess layer on the top of electrolyte, tool or the work piece
- Not be toxic and corrosive
- Economical and easily available.

3.4 Mechanical system – It consist of the table, the frame, work enclosure (prevents the electrolyte from spilling), the work head (where the tool is mounted).The tools (electrodes) are also part of the mechanical system. One of the most important parameters of electrochemical machining is maintaining a constant voltage level. This is achieved by the control system providing a movement of the tool at a constant speed equal to the linear rate of machining. The process in a steady state is performed at a constant (typically gap 0.1-0.4 mm / 0.004-0.016”).

A firm fixation of the work piece provided by the fixture, the table and the frame is also important for stable operation of the system at a constant gap. Conventional machining equipment including CNC machines may be modified for electrochemical machining process.

Figure 2: Simple working principle

The figure 2 shows that the work piece is mounted in a fixture electrically isolated from the tank and other machine parts. The work piece is connected to the positive terminal (anode) of the Power Supply. The tool is connected to the negative terminal (cathode). The electrolyte is continuously flowing through a hole in the tool to the gap between the work piece and the tool surfaces. The tool is moving towards the work piece at a constant speed. The gap between the tool and the work piece is kept constant.

Literature survey on ECM recent developments:

During ECM, hydrogen gas is generated in the form of gas bubble while some by-product will also form at IEG. This will reduce the conductivity of electrolyte and affect the MRR (Fang et al., 2017). Fang et al., (2017) have implemented large amplitude vibrations in wire ECM to encourage the bubble removal and electrolyte renewal. Wire ECM is ECM that uses metallic wire as tool to carry out machining. Vibrating tool will help gas to escape. As result, a large-amplitude vibration of ribbed wire electrode will encourage the bubble removal process and improve the MRR and matching efficiency.

WECM is a variant of ECM. It uses a metal wire as the tool cathode and removes material by anodic electrochemical dissolution, and the part is formed with the relative motion between the wire electrode and the work piece. It has great advantages and well surface integrity such as no dependence on mechanical properties of the material being machined, no tool wear, no residual stress, no recast layers and heat-affected zones (Zeng et al., 2012). Hence, it is a potential method for processing parts with ruled surfaces which is hard to machine like the fir-tree slots in a turbine disc (Klocke et al., 2018a).

In WECM, the machining gap is usually tens of microns down to only a few microns, making it very difficult to rapid remove electrolytic products entirely from such a small gap. Much

research has been conducted to improve the outcome of WECM on thick work pieces, and they can be divided into two categories according to the electrolyte flow status. In the first category, the work piece is immersed in electrolyte, and the electrolyte in machining gap flows following the electrode movement (Fang et al., 2017; Kalaimathi et al., 2017; Xian he et al., 2017).

The second category is axial electrolyte flushing (Klocke et al., 2018 b). The electrolyte with a certain pressure is ejected from the nozzle, and flows into the machining gap along the electrode, which brings the electrolyte products out of the machining gap from top to bottom. High-speed flushing is the most commonly used method to promote electrolyte renewal and replenishment. Although the above methods do accelerate the electrolyte renewal and the products removal, but the flow path is very long, meaning that fresh electrolyte has relatively to travel far to reach the reaction area. Hence, research is carried out to create a relatively short flow path (Xu et al., 2020).

A pulsating radial electrolyte supply in WECM is proposed to improve the machining capability for thick work piece. The tool is a tube electrode with a line of micro-holes on cylindrical surface. The processing of micro-holes in the tube electrode using a rotating helical electrode is shown in Figure 2. It was shown experimentally that using a tube electrode with holes of varying diameters as a tool electrode provides better process capacity for pulsating radial electrolyte supply in WECM. Machining accuracy, efficiency, and quality in WECM are influenced by different electrolytic factors, power factors, vibration amplitude and frequency of tool or work piece, thickness and feed rate of tool or work piece. Amongst various tool materials, tungsten is most widely used due to its high tensile strength and excellent chemical stability. Ribbed wire, textured wire, helical tools, cutting edge tools, and fluted tools have been used for enhancing flushing in WECM.

Baoji et al., 2019 carried out a study on magnetic field-assisted ECM drilling. The ECM was assisted with magnetic field that suppresses anodic dissolution and magnetic field that promotes anodic dissolution. Results show that ECM localization was enhanced under magnetic field that suppresses anodic dissolution while not benefited under magnetic field that promotes anodic dissolution.

A study was carried out by Ridha et al., 2015 to combine the use of magnetic abrasive finishing (MAF) and ECM to decrease the machining time. Comparison of machining time between conventional MAF and combination of MAF and ECM was done. As result, the combination of MAF and ECM was able to achieve similar surface roughness as conventional MAF by using 60% to 70% of time used by conventional MAF.

A study was done to implement the use of ultrasonic in jet-ECM to overcome the formation of passivation layers (Clare & Mitchell-Smith, 2016). Jet-ECM is ECM with electrolyte injected to ease the removal of removed material from the work piece. During the ECM of certain material, such as Titanium, passivation layers might form around the work piece in the form of oxides. These layers will suppress material removal and reduce surface finish of the work piece. In this study, ultrasonic was found to be able to reduce the formation of passivating layers by 23% at selected frequency, and the Ra was reduced by 31%.

According to Mohd Adnan et al., 2013, fuzzy logic (FL) is capable to converse, reason and make rational decisions in an environment of imperfect information. FL involves fuzzifier process, rules, membership function, and defuzzification. Fuzzier process is the process of transforming fuzzy set data into suitable linguistic values by the definition of linguistic variables the types of membership function (MF), which defines the way of input being mapped

to a membership value. Fuzzy rules are set of linguistic statements which establish the relationship between the input and the output in a fuzzy system. Fuzzy rule is obtained based on experimental work and knowledge. Defuzzification will be used to generate a non-fuzzy decision.

FL has been widely used in machining due to their similar features in input and output (Mohd et al., 2013). FL is said to be able to implement in machining as the input of FL in machining can be indicated as different types of machining parameter while output of FL can represent the machining performance. FL has been used for various purpose in machining. Some researchers have used FL to determine the output of machining (Balasubramanian et al., 2016; Hossain et al., 2016; Mohamad et al., 2010). Besides, some of the researchers implemented FL into machining to investigate the applicable of controlling the machining performance through FL (Sadegh, 2017; Labib et al., 2011). There were also researchers tried to implement FL to obtain the optimum machining parameters (Chakraborty et al., 2018; Teimouri & Sohrabpoor, 2013).

A new ECM method, electrochemical machining with electrolyte confined by absorption material (ECM-ECAM) was proposed. Because of the physical properties of the absorption material, dissolution of work piece material is restricted in the contacting area between the work piece and the absorption material. Experimental results showed that the new processing method is effective and has a certain positive impact on the machining accuracy. In addition, the continuous ECM-ECAM was realized by rotating and cleaning the absorption felt during machining. (Watara Natsu et al., 2020)

WECM is used for the machining of cylindrical work pieces which suitable for turning a very thin-walled tubes, which is difficult to perform using a conventional machining method. The ECM performance can be improved by combining with other processes such as MAF and Jet-ECM. The recent developments of FL by integrating different algorithm into FL also show a promising future of ECM as most of the results are accurate and reliable after being tested (Chan Jia Yuan et al., 2021).

From the Literature survey, the advantages of ECM over traditional methods such as Abrasive water jet and Milling process are listed as: ECM is well suited for the machining of complex two-dimensional shapes. Delicate parts and poorly machinable materials are easily made. Little or no tool wear is needed. Its disadvantages as Initial tooling can be time consuming and costly. Environmentally harmful by-products and large power consumption (Chan Jia Yuan et al., 2021).

APPLICATIONS OF ECM:

- Used in producing hole (circular and non-circular) production, profiling and contouring of components, engine casting features, turbine blade shaping, dies for forging, gun barrel rifling, honeycomb structures and irregular shapes, and burr free parts.
- Complex shapes to be obtained without distortion, cracks, burrs, white layer, heat-affected zone or residual stress.
- Raj et al., 2019 lists some of the typical applications - Machining of cavities in forging dies, drilling deeper holes and irregular shaped holes which cannot be obtained by conventional machining methods.
- Machining of complex profiles like turbine wheels, turbine and jet blades.
- Die sinking: Electro Chemical Machining is often used as an alternative to the cavity type electric discharge machining (EDM).

- Fabrication of thin-walled parts: Electrochemical machining does not produce surface stress in the work piece therefore even very brittle and easily deformed materials may be machined in thin-walled shapes.
- Grinding of a work piece by a rotating wheel, which performs grinding operation through an electrolyte. The wheel is conductive and cathodically connected. Non-conductive hard particles are set on the wheel surface. The particles provide a constant gap through which an electrolyte is continuously fed. Hard and brittle materials are ground by the method.
- Rough corners or edges can be turned into very smooth parts and the process is known as deburring.
- WECM can prove to be an inexpensive way of micro-turning as diamond tip tool inserts, generally used in micro turning, are relatively expensive. Another application of WECM in turning can be in machining micro threads on dental implants.

CONCLUSION:

Electro Chemical Machining is possible for processing all groups of constructional steels and alloys used in the industry, including high-strength steels and alloys, metal-ceramics, nanostructure alloys. This materials such as alloy steels and construction steels, corrosive resistant steels, high-carbon chromium steels, stainless chrome-nickel steels, tool steels, chromium-nickel heat-resistant alloys, HSS, copper and copper alloys, nickel and nickel alloys, magnets, titanium and its alloys, ceramic-metal hard alloys (WC-Co, WC-TiC-Co), nanostructure steels and alloys could be easily machined by Electro Chemical Machining.

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